

Feasibility of a solely acoustic-wave-driven light amplifier

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In Brillouin and Raman lasers, light is amplified by an input pump light through the excited acoustic and molecular oscillations in a medium. However, can medium oscillations alone amplify light in a realistic photonic circuit? Here, we demonstrate that modulating an optical resonator by a traveling wave having the frequency and phase velocity much smaller than the frequency and phase velocity of light can result in dramatically large light amplification accompanied with conversion to multiple comb lines within a relatively small frequency band. Our calculations show that the proposed light amplifier can be realized in a lithium niobate racetrack resonator with millimeter-scale perimeter modulated by a surface acoustic wave with a surprisingly small amplitude and with the propagation constant satisfying the Brillouin phase matching condition.

Keywords: amplification of light; traveling wave modulation; optical waveguides, optical microresonators, optical frequency combs; acoustic waves.

The growing interest in exploring wave propagation through media *parametrically modulated in time and space* is driven by its intriguing features – not possible in the stationary case – along with current and potential applications [1-3]. Numerous earlier and recent papers investigated modulation-induced amplification of waves [4-18], signal processing [19-24], frequency comb generation [25-28], and sideband transitions including the effects of propagation nonreciprocity and complete inelastic transparency [29-39]. Temporal modulation can also create dynamic bandgaps where waves with certain frequencies are trapped in localized regions [35, 40, 41]. Modulating the properties of a medium can affect the group velocity of waves, resulting in slow or fast light [42]. Temporal modulation also allows for real-time wavefront control, enabling dynamic beam steering, focusing, and diffraction pattern manipulation, which are important in adaptive optics and beamforming technologies [43].

A crucial feature of wave propagation in a time-modulated medium is the potential for amplification. Modulation can transfer energy to the wave, enhancing its amplitude, or can extract energy from it, leading to attenuation. For example, temporal modulation of the medium refractive index $\Delta n(t) = \Delta n_p \cos(\omega_p t)$ with frequency ω_p close to a multiple of the input electromagnetic wave half-frequency, $\omega_0/2$, can lead to amplification or attenuation of this wave described by Floquet theory (see e.g., [11, 44]). For applications in optics, the amplification is customarily achieved by pumping with a high-power light which frequency ω_p is *comparable* to the frequency of input light to be amplified, $\omega_p/\omega_0 \sim 1$ [45]. For example, in Brillouin and Raman lasers, the acoustic and molecular vibrations are excited by a pump light with a frequency ω_p that is relatively close to the frequency of amplified light, commonly with $|\omega_p - \omega_0| \ll \omega_p$ [46-49].

However, is it possible to amplify an optical wave with frequency ω_0 in a realistic photonic circuit modulated *solely by a travelling wave with a much smaller frequency* $\omega_p \ll \omega_0$ (e.g., by an acoustic or RF wave) in the absence of pumping light? For an ideal waveguide with *negligible dispersion and losses over the large bandwidth* $\Delta\omega_B \gtrsim \omega_0$, a positive answer to this question was given several decades ago [8, 9]. The authors of Ref. [8, 9] (and, independently, the authors of Ref. [14]) found the exact solution of this problem for a one-dimensional propagation of a wave in a medium with constant impedance modulated by a traveling wave [8] and its asymptotic (eikonal, WKB) solution for a medium with constant permeability [9, 14]. It was shown that, under these conditions, amplification is indeed possible if the phase velocity of light v_0 is close to the phase velocity v_p of the traveling wave. These results are irrelevant to realistic photonic circuits since their transmission loss and dispersion are *never negligible within the frequency bandwidth* $\Delta\omega_B \gtrsim \omega_0$ required for the observation of substantial amplification [6, 9, 15]. Consequently, the intriguing question if light amplification can be achieved by modulating a photonic circuit solely with a traveling wave having frequency $\omega_p \ll \omega_0$ remains open.

Here, we suggest an answer to this question. We demonstrate that light propagating through an optical racetrack resonator with realistic characteristics can be significantly amplified by an acoustic wave with a

surprisingly small practically achievable amplitude. The amplification occurs within a narrow bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$ near the Brillouin phase matching condition $\omega_p/v_p \cong 2\omega_0/v_0$. The developed theory is valid under the assumption of sufficiently small power of light inside the resonator introducing negligible nonlinear effects. In the examples considered, the input light wave with frequency ω_0 is converted into multiple frequency comb lines separated by ω_p within a relatively small bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$ where the maximum comb line power significantly exceeds the power of the input wave.

Fig. 1. An optical waveguide (a) and resonator (b) with the refractive index modulated by a traveling wave attenuating with distance along the waveguide.

The effect of modulation can be better understood by comparing light propagation in an open waveguide (Fig. 1(a)) and in a resonator formed by a closed waveguide (Fig. 1(b)). In both cases, we assume that the propagation of light along the waveguide is described by the wave equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 (n^2 E)}{\partial t^2} - c^2 \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad (1)$$

where $n(x, t)$ is the refractive index, $E(x, t)$ is the electric field, and c is the speed of light.

We start with a brief description of light propagating in an *open waveguide*. The input optical wave is defined by the boundary condition at $x < 0$ for the input wave $E_{in}(x, t) = \exp(i\omega_0(x/v_0 - t))$ (Fig. 1(a)). The dependence of refractive index on time t and coordinate x along the waveguide is set to

$$n(x, t) = n_0 + i\eta_0 + \Delta n_p \cos\left(\omega_p \left(t - \frac{x}{v_p}\right)\right) \exp(-\alpha_p x), \quad (2)$$

$$\eta_0 = \frac{\alpha_0 c}{\omega_0},$$

for $0 < x < L$ and $n(x, t) = n_0$ elsewhere. In this equation, ω_p and v_p are the frequency and phase velocity of the modulating wave, c is the speed of light, while α_0 and α_p define the attenuation of optical and modulating wave amplitudes. The modulation amplitude is assumed small, $\Delta n_p \ll n_0$. For $\alpha_p = 0$, Eq. (2) describes a travelling wave which has constant amplitude Δn_p within the interval $0 < x < L$ and vanishes outside it. Eqs. (1) and (2) neglect the waveguide dispersion. We will justify this assumption for sufficiently small transmission bandwidths that are considered below.

To estimate the *maximum possible* amplification of light in an open waveguide, we first consider the effect of modulation with zero attenuation, $\alpha_p = 0$. For modulation relatively slow in time and space when

$$\frac{\omega_p}{\omega_0} \ll 1, \quad \frac{k_p}{k_0} = \frac{\omega_p v_0}{v_p \omega_0} \ll 1, \quad (3)$$

solution of Eq. (1) can be found in the eikonal (semiclassical, WKB) approximation [50-54] as described in [55], Section A. Then, for the practically feasible case when the output light bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B(L)$ and attenuation α_0 are relatively small, $\Delta\omega_B(L) \ll \omega_0$, and $\alpha_0 L \ll 1$, we find ([55], Sections C and D):

$$P_{av}(L) \cong 1 + \frac{(v_0 - 2v_p)(v_0 - 3v_p)}{v_p^2} \left(\frac{\Delta\omega_B(L)}{4\omega_0}\right)^2 - 2\alpha_0 L. \quad (4)$$

It directly follows from this equation that *significant amplification of light by a travelling wave with the phase velocity comparable to or larger than the phase velocity of light, $v_p \gtrsim v_0$, is impossible*, confirming earlier results [6, 9, 15]. Indeed, we find from Eq. (4) that then $P_{av}(L) - 1 \sim (\Delta\omega_B(L)/\omega_0)^2 - 2\alpha_0 L$, while, in realistic photonic waveguides, a low-loss bandwidth always satisfies the condition $\omega_B(L) < \omega_0$. In

particular, this conclusion is valid for the case of synchronous modulation, $v_p = v_0$, and instantaneous modulation, $v_p = \infty$.

It also follows from Eq. (4) that for small $v_p \ll v_0$ the amplification grows proportionally to $(v_0/v_p)^2$. However, the eikonal solution of the wave equation leading to Eq. (4) does not allow us to consider sufficiently small values of v_p since, according to Eq. (3), the condition of slowness of modulation in space restricts these values to $v_p \gg \omega_p v_0 / \omega_0$. Fortunately, for small $v_p \ll v_0$, the restriction $\omega_p / v_p \ll \omega_0 / v_0$ of Eq. (3) can be withdrawn and solution of the wave equation, Eq. (1), can be found by the regular perturbation theory over $\Delta n_p / n_0$. We note here that the perturbation theory is incorrect if the phase velocities v_p and v_0 are close to each other so that $|v_p - v_0| / v_0 \sim \Delta n_p / n_0 \ll 1$ [56]. In the latter case the eikonal theory can be applied [50, 51]. Additionally, calculations detailed in Appendix A and Section E of [55] show that, in the absence of attenuation of modulation, $\alpha_p = 0$, the first order perturbation over $\Delta n_p / n_0$ fails tending to infinity near the singularity determined by the Brillouin resonance condition

$$\omega_p = \omega_p^{(res)} = \frac{2\omega_0 v_p}{v_0 + v_p}. \quad (5)$$

For finite α_p , under the conditions of our interest, $v_p \ll v_0$ and $\omega_p \ll \omega_0$, and for the commonly valid condition $\alpha_p v_p \ll \omega_p$, the maximum averaged over time amplification of light propagating along the waveguide with the length exceeding α_p^{-1} is determined at the resonance modulation frequency $\omega_p^{(res)}$ as ([55], Section E)

$$P_{av}(L) \cong 1 + \left(\frac{\Delta n_p \omega_0}{2n_0 \alpha_p v_0} \right)^2 - 2\alpha_0 L. \quad (6)$$

As an example, we estimate the effect of light amplification by a surface acoustic wave (SAW) which can be launched into an optical waveguide with an interdigital transducer (IDT) (see e.g., [34, 38] and Fig. 2). We consider light with frequency $\omega_0 = 2\pi \cdot 193$ THz propagating along a lithium niobate (LN) waveguide with refractive index $n_0 = 2.2$ [57]. For a SAW, we set $v_p \sim 4000$ m/s, which yields $\omega_p \cong \frac{2\omega_0 v_p}{v_0} \sim 2\pi \cdot 10$ GHz. Setting $\Delta n_p \cong 10^{-4}$, $\alpha_0 = 0$, and $\alpha_p \cong 20$ dB/cm, which is the smallest demonstrated attenuation at this modulation frequency in the bulk LN [58], we have $P_{av} - 1 \cong 0.2$. For a larger initial index modulation, which is much more challenging to achieve, the amplification may become comparable with

the original light power and the perturbation approach fails. A more advanced design of a *no-light-involved* traveling wave generator can include a set of IDTs positioned along a waveguide (see e.g., [38]) which can marginally increase the amplification effect though in a quite ineffective way.

Overall, our estimates based on Eqs. (4) and (6) indicate that significant amplification of light in an open optical waveguide is currently unfeasible.

Fig. 2. Illustration of an optical waveguide modulated by a SAW.

A qualitatively different situation leading to a large modulation-induced amplification of light occurs in an *optical resonator*. We consider now a closed optical waveguide with length $2L$ forming a racetrack resonator which is coupled to an input-output waveguide as illustrated in Fig. 1(b). We assume, again, that the modulation is described by Eq. (1) with the refractive index defined by Eq. (2) and takes place along a length L of the resonator waveguide. The monochromatic input light in the input-output waveguide near the center of the coupling region $x = x_0$ is set to $E_{in}(x, t) = \exp(i\omega_0(x/v_0 - t))$. Using the transfer matrix approach (see, e.g., [59]), we find the output light field $E_{out}(t)$ from the equation

$$\begin{pmatrix} E_{out}(t) \\ E(x_0, t) \end{pmatrix} = S \begin{pmatrix} E_{in}(t) \\ E(2L + x_0, t) \end{pmatrix}, \quad S = \begin{pmatrix} \tau & \kappa \\ -\kappa & \tau \end{pmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where matrix S is the unitary S-matrix, so that $\tau^2 + \kappa^2 = 1$. In this equation, the coordinates $x = 2L + x_0$ and $x = x_0$ define the beginning and the end of the coupling region and the S-matrix parameters κ and τ determine the coupling between the input-output waveguide and resonator (Fig. 1(b)). Then, the output field $E_{out}(t)$ is determined by the frequency comb expansion

$$E_{out}(t) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} U_m^{(c)} \exp[i(m\omega_p - \omega_0)t]. \quad (8)$$

where the expression of the frequency comb amplitudes $U_m^{(c)}$ through the system parameters presented in Appendix B is determined in full analogy with calculations of Ref. [60]. Consequently, the total time-averaged output power is

$$P_{av} = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} |U_m^{(c)}|^2. \quad (9)$$

The output power is maximized at the resonance optical frequencies

$$\omega_{0,q}^{(res)} = \frac{2\pi q}{T}, \quad q \gg 1, \text{ integer.} \quad (10)$$

and at the resonance modulation frequencies

$$\omega_{p,N}^{(res)} = \frac{2\pi N}{T}, \quad N = 1, 2, \dots \quad (11)$$

both expressed through the circulation time of light along the resonator perimeter $T = 2L/v_0$. The quality factor of our resonator is determined as

$$Q = \frac{\omega_0}{2} \left(\alpha_0 v_0 + \frac{\kappa^2}{2T} \right)^{-1}. \quad (12)$$

Close to these resonance frequencies and for sufficiently small propagation loss α_0 , the bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$ of transmission spectrum defined by Eq. (8) can significantly increase. This occurs due to the zero eigenfrequency dispersion and small frequency-independent loss α_0 assumed in our model. To shrink the transmission bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$ to a practical value, we can introduce an *offset* $\Delta\omega_p$ from the modulation resonance $\omega_{p,N}^{(res)}$ defined by Eq. (11). This idea is prompted by calculations of Ref. [61]. The transmission spectra in Fig. 5(b) of Ref. [61] for instantaneous modulation ($v_p = \infty$), suggests that choosing an appropriate offset $\Delta\omega_p$ we can shrink the transmission bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$ and simultaneously increase the transmission power within this bandwidth. A similar approach can be used for the travelling wave modulation considered here. Choosing a transmission band with a relatively small width (which, in practice, corresponds to the band with the smallest possible material loss and dispersion) we can redirect and amplify light within this band only.

Fig. 3. Transmission power spectra for a racetrack resonator modulated by a SAW. Common parameters for all plots are indicated at the top of the figure. Other parameters are indicated at the top of each plot.

Our calculations ([55], Section F) show that, similar to an open waveguide, significant amplification of light by modulation with a travelling wave having the phase velocity v_p larger than or comparable with the phase velocity of light v_0 is unfeasible. However, the amplification effect can increase for small $v_p \ll v_0$ and boost near to the Brillouin resonance defined by Eq. (5). In this case, simple analytical expressions for the transmission power spectrum $|U_m^{(c)}|^2$ and bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$ are given in Appendix B, showing that $\Delta\omega_B$ is inverse proportional to the modulation frequency offset $\Delta\omega_p$. Numerical examples presented in Fig. 3

demonstrate the dramatically large modulation-induced amplification of light in an optical resonator accompanied with conversion to multiple comb lines within a relatively small frequency band. As shown below, this amplification effect is possible to achieve experimentally.

In the plots of transmission power spectra shown in Fig. 3, we set the coupling coefficient $\kappa = 0.1$ in Figs. (a), (c)-(f) and $\kappa = 0.03$ in Fig. 3(b), light frequency $\omega_0 = 2\pi \cdot 193$ THz, and refractive index of LN $n_0 = 2.2$ resulting in the phase velocity of light $v_0 = c/n_0 = 1.36 \cdot 10^8$ m/s. The traveling wave velocity is set equal to the characteristic SAW velocity in LN, $v_p = 3500$ m/s [62]. The modulation frequency used in our calculations, $\omega_p^{(res)} \cong 2\pi \cdot 9.9042$ GHz, is close to the value defined by Eq. (5), which was optimized to arrive at a larger amplification. The required precision of this value will be discussed below. The half-length of the resonator perimeter $L = 6.89$ mm is calculated from the modulation resonance condition of Eq. (11) for $N = 1$ and $\omega_{p,1}^{(res)} = \omega_p^{(res)}$. The positive shift of the output frequency comb spectra relative to the input frequency ω_0 in the plots of Fig. 3 is explained by the enhancement of the amplification effect when the co-propagating acoustic wave and light approach the Brillouin resonance. The shift will become negative for their contra-propagation when the sign of v_p is changed from positive to negative (see also discussion in [55], Section F).

To arrive at the practically feasible *negligibly small resonator eigenfrequency dispersion*, we set the transmission bandwidth in all plots in Fig. 3 equal to $\Delta\omega_B \cong 0.5$ THz. This was achieved by choosing an appropriate resonance modulation frequency offset $\Delta\omega_p \sim 1$ MHz for each of the plots in this figure. We show in Appendix C, that for all the examples considered in Fig. 3 the eigenfrequency dispersion is possible to reduce to negligible values by the waveguide dispersion optimization demonstrated experimentally [63, 64].

Other resonator and modulation parameters in Fig. 3 are the modulation amplitude and attenuation, Δn_p and α_p , and the resonator waveguide loss and quality-factor, α_0 and Q . As we show below, the values of these parameters are justified based on their experimental feasibility and validity of the approximations made.

We start with the consideration of Fig. 3(a), where we set the modulation amplitude $\Delta n_p = 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$, modulation attenuation $\alpha_p = 30$ dB/cm, the resonator waveguide loss $\alpha_0 = 5$ dB/m, and find its quality-factor equal to $Q = 9.45 \cdot 10^6$. For these parameters, the total amplification of the light power demonstrated in this figure has a dramatically large value of $P_{av} = 107.1$ dB.

The LN *waveguide propagation loss* substantially smaller than $\alpha_0 = 5$ dB/m assumed in Fig. 3(a) has been recently demonstrated experimentally [65-67]. In particular, an LN resonator with remarkably small waveguide loss 0.34 dB/m approaching the bulk material loss was achieved by chemo-mechanical waveguide polishing in Ref. [65]. The waveguide loss as small as 0.2 dB/m was demonstrated in Ref. [66] by post-fabrication annealing in oxygen atmosphere. The authors of Ref. [67] developed a robust method

for fabrication of thin-film lithium niobate waveguides, which is based on dry reactive ion etching, with an ultra-low propagation loss as small as 1.3 dB/m. A critical requirement for maximizing the resonator Q-factor is the suppression of the nonlinear effects leading to the attenuation of light at the input frequency ω_0 . It has been shown in Ref. [66] that the experimentally observed Q-factor $\sim 10^7$ in an LN ring resonator is not affected by nonlinear effects if the inter-resonator light power is ~ 1 mW or smaller. Then, for the case considered in Fig. 3(a) with coupling coefficient $\kappa = 0.1$ and ~ 100 dB amplification, the output power will not exceed ~ 10 μ W, while the input light power has to be as small as 1 fW. For a smaller amplification of ~ 20 dB, the input and output light power can be of the order of 1 μ W and 10 μ W, respectively. Here we do not address a more complex question if a larger inter-resonator power, which generates essential nonlinear effects, can still coexist with significant modulation-induced amplification of light.

Different approaches have been developed for the effective *refractive index modulation* of optical waveguides (see [20, 22, 34, 38, 68-73] and references therein). In particular, an IDT with feasible parameters can generate a SAW inducing the refractive index modulation $\Delta n_p \sim 10^{-4}$ (see Appendix D) which experiences strong attenuation with distance from the IDT. In LN, at modulation frequency $\omega_p \cong 10$ GHz, the SAW attenuation has the smallest experimentally achieved value of $\alpha_p \cong 20$ dB/cm [58]. Consequently, in Fig. 3(a) we set the experimentally feasible $\alpha_p = 30$ dB/cm, and the initial refractive index modulation amplitude $\Delta n_p = 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$. Generally, a combination of in-phase tilted IDTs distributed along an optical waveguide and generating properly aligned SAWs can increase the induced refractive index modulation amplitude (see e.g., [38]). In the design of such advanced modulation devices, the proximity of IDTs to the optical waveguide leading to the enhancement of modulation strength should be compromised with their effect on the optical waveguide loss.

For comparison with Fig. 3(a), in Figs. 3(b)-(d), the amplification effect is demonstrated when the values of modulation amplitude and attenuation, as well as of the waveguide loss, are changed to those even easier to reach. In Fig. 3(b), the initial refractive index modulation amplitude is changed to $\Delta n_p = 5 \cdot 10^{-6}$, i.e., four times smaller than that in Fig. 3(a). It is seen, that in this case a substantial amplification of $P_{av} = 32.2$ dB can be achieved provided that the coupling coefficient is reduced to $\kappa = 0.03$ and Q-factor increased to $Q = 1.45 \cdot 10^7$. In Fig. 3(c), for the modulation attenuation increased to $\alpha_p = 60$ dB/cm, we calculate an amplification of $P_{av} = 76.8$ dB. In Fig. 3(d), for the increased waveguide loss $\alpha_0 = 10$ dB/m corresponding to the reduced resonator quality factor $Q = 5.85 \cdot 10^6$, the amplification is still impressively large and equal to $P_{av} = 71.9$ dB.

Finally, we estimate the required tuning precision of the modulation frequency ω_p and the effect of additional reduction of transmission bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$. In Fig. 3(e), the modulation frequency is decreased by $2\pi \cdot 0.1$ MHz to $2\pi \cdot 9.9041$ GHz while all other parameters in this figure are kept the same as in Fig. 3(a). This shift results in the reduction of amplification to $P_{av} = 88.4$ dB and the reduction of transmission

bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$ by approximately 0.05 THz. In turn, Fig. 3(f) shows that further reduction of the transmission bandwidth to $\Delta\omega_B \cong 0.2$ THz (here we set the offset $\Delta\omega_p = 10$ MHz compared to $\Delta\omega_p = 5$ MHz in Fig. 3(a)) significantly reduces the amplification power to $P_{av} = 41.5$ dB.

In conclusion, we demonstrated that dramatic amplification of light is possible in an acoustically modulated optical racetrack resonator. To arrive at the feasible system parameters enabling the amplification, we noticed that the transmission bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$ of a resonator can be controlled and made small by shifting the modulation frequency ω_p from the exact resonance $\omega_{p,N}^{(res)}$ defined by Eq. (11). We showed that the amplification effect can be radically enhanced near the Brillouin phase matching condition $v_0\omega_p = 2v_p\omega_0$. As an example, we demonstrated that amplification of the full power of light exceeding 100 dB can be achieved within the bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B = 0.5$ THz in a LN racetrack optical resonator with the waveguide half-length 6.89 mm and loss 5 dB/m modulated by acoustic waves with velocity $v_p = 3500$ m/s, initial modulation index $\Delta n_p = 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$, and attenuation 30 dB/cm (Fig. 3(a)). Reducing the modulation index amplitude to a very small value $\Delta n_p = 5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ still results in amplification exceeding 30 dB (Fig. 3(b)). We showed that all the resonator and modulation parameters required to arrive at the demonstrated amplification of light are currently feasible. While the developed theory assumes that the power of light inside the resonator is small enough not to introduce essential nonlinear effects, it is interesting to investigate if these effects can coexist with modulation-induced amplification. On the other hand, since the developed theory assumes very low input light power, it is interesting to explore its quantum version and investigate if the proposed device can amplify single-photon or few-photon signals. We suggest that further optimization of the parameters of our model, along with the advanced design of photonic circuits that incorporate modulation elements, will enable the practical realization of the proposed acoustic light amplifier with the predicted exceptional performance.

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Appendix A

Solution of Eq. (1) by the perturbation theory

In our solution of Eq. (1), we distinguish two cases. If the phase velocity of the modulating wave has the same order as or larger than that of light, $v_p \gtrsim v_0$, then, under the condition of our interest, $\omega_p \ll \omega_0$, this solution can be found in the eikonal approximation [9, 50, 51], also known as the WKB and semiclassical approximation in quantum mechanics [52-54] valid under the condition of Eq. (3) (see sections C and D of

[55]). Alternatively, if $v_p \ll v_0$, the second inequality in Eq. (3) may fail, but then solution of Eq. (1) can be found with a regular perturbation theory over $\Delta n_p/n_0$ setting

$$E(x, t) = E^{(0)}(x, t)e^{-\alpha_0 x} \left(1 + \Delta U_p(x, t)\right), \quad (\text{A1})$$

where $|\Delta U_p(x, t)| \ll 1$. Then, calculations detailed in [55], Section E, yield in the first order over $\Delta n_p/n_0$:

$$\Delta U_p(x, t) = i\Omega_p(x) \cos \left(\omega_p \left(t - \frac{v_0 + v_p}{2v_0 v_p} x \right) - iG_p(x) \right), \quad (\text{A2})$$

where

$$\Omega_p(x) = -2i\sqrt{\Delta U^+ \Delta U^- W^+(x) W^-(x)}, \quad G_p(x) = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{\Delta U^- W^-(x)}{\Delta U^+ W^+(x)} \right), \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$W^\pm(x) = \sin \left(\pm \frac{v_0 - v_p}{2v_0 v_p} \omega_p x + \frac{i\alpha_p}{2} x \right) \exp \left(-\frac{\alpha_p}{2} x \right), \quad (\text{A4})$$

$$\Delta U^\pm = \frac{\Delta n_p v_p^2 (\omega_0 \pm \omega_p)^2}{n_0 \left[\pm \omega_p (v_0 - v_p) + i\alpha_p v_0 v_p \right] \left[2\omega_0 v_p \pm \omega_p (v_0 + v_p) + i\alpha_p v_0 v_p \right]}. \quad (\text{A5})$$

This solution is valid only if $|\Delta U_p(x, t)| \ll 1$, or

$$|\Delta U^\pm| \ll 1. \quad (\text{A6})$$

Presenting Eq. (A1) in the form $E(x, t) = E_0(x, t) \exp(-\alpha_0 x) \exp(\Delta U_p(x, t))$, which is valid for $|\Delta U_p(x, t)| \ll 1$, we reveal the physical meaning of $\Omega_p(x)$ in Eq. (A3) as a *modulation index* (see [20, 24, 25], and [55], Section D).

For the zero attenuation of modulation, $\alpha_p = 0$, the denominator in the expressions for ΔU^\pm vanishes at the synchronous modulation condition, $v_p = v_0$. However, this condition does not lead to the singularity of $\Delta U_p(x, t)$ since then functions $W^\pm(x)$ vanish as well. Nevertheless, at $v_p \rightarrow v_0$ the value of $W^\pm(L)$ and, thus, $\Delta U_p(L, t)$ becomes proportional to the modulation length L and can significantly increase together

with it. The amplification of output power in this case is still limited by Eq. (A6). In contrast, for $\alpha_p = 0$, the determined solution *possesses a singularity* at

$$2\omega_0 v_p = \pm \omega_p (v_0 + v_p), \quad (\text{A7})$$

where ΔU^\pm can significantly grow, yet under the restriction of Eq. (A6). The sign \pm in Eq. (A7) corresponds to the co- and contra-propagating light and traveling waves. Naturally, Eq. (A7) coincides with the phase matching condition for the backward Brillouin scattering [45]. For the case of our concern, $v_p \ll v_0$ and $\omega_p \ll \omega_0$, this singularity, missed in the eikonal approximation, takes place close to the condition when the propagation constant k_p of the traveling wave is twice as large as the propagation constant k_0 of light, i.e., at $\omega_p/v_p = 2\omega_0/v_0$, similar to the Brillouin scattering. For determinacy, here we consider the resonance frequency corresponding to sign $+$ in Eq. (A7) (see Eq. (5)).

Appendix B

Frequency comb expansion of the transmission amplitude through an optical resonator

The frequency comb amplitudes $U_m^{(c)}$ in Eq. (8) are determined by the expansion ([55], Section F):

$$U_m^{(c)} = \tau \delta_{0m} - \kappa^2 \exp \left[im \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{\omega_p T}{2} - \frac{\omega_p (v_0 + v_p)}{2v_0 v_p} L - iG_p(L) \right) \right] \times \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} J_n(\sigma_{n+1} \Omega_p(L)) \tau^n \exp \left[(n+1) \left(-\frac{im}{2} \omega_p T + i\omega_0 T - 2\alpha_0 L \right) \right], \quad (\text{B1})$$

$$\sigma_n = \frac{\sin\left(\frac{n}{2} \omega_p T\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{1}{2} \omega_p T\right)}, \quad T = \frac{2L}{v_0}.$$

Here, δ_{nm} is the Kronecker delta, $J_m(z)$ is the Bessel function, and T is the circulation time of light. For the case of our interest here, $v_p \ll v_0$, functions $G_p(L)$ and $\Omega_p(L)$ are defined within the perturbation theory by Eq. (A3), while their expressions in the eikonal approximation are given in [55], Section D.

At the exact Brillouin and optical resonance defined by Eqs. (5) and (10), small modulation index, $|\Omega_p(L)| \ll 1$, and close to the modulation resonance $|\Delta\omega_p|T \ll 1$, $\Delta\omega_p = \omega_p - \omega_{p,N}^{(res)}$ (see Eq. (11)), the absolute value of the frequency comb amplitudes defined by Eq. (B1) are simplified to ([55], Section F):

$$|U_m^{(c)}| = \left| \tau \delta_{0m} - \frac{i\kappa^2}{\Delta\omega_p T} \left(\frac{\Delta n_p \omega_0}{4n_0 \Delta\omega_p L \alpha_p} \right)^{|m|} \frac{\Gamma\left(i \frac{4\alpha_0 L + \kappa^2}{\Delta\omega_p T}\right)}{\Gamma\left(|m| + 1 + i \frac{4\alpha_0 L + \kappa^2}{\Delta\omega_p T}\right)} \right|. \quad (\text{B2})$$

From this equation, the characteristic transmission bandwidth is found as

$$\Delta\omega_B = \frac{\Delta n_p \omega_0 \omega_p}{2n_0 \Delta\omega_p L \alpha_p}. \quad (\text{B3})$$

At the same time, a necessary condition of the amplification effect found from Eq. (B2) in [55], Section F, is

$$\frac{\Delta\omega_B}{2\omega_p} = \frac{\Delta n_p \omega_0}{4n_0 \Delta\omega_p L \alpha_p} \gg 1. \quad (\text{B4})$$

As expected, Eqs. (B3) and (B4) shows that small shift $\Delta\omega_p$ from the modulation resonance required for amplification necessitates the increase in transmission bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$.

Appendix C

Eigenfrequency dispersion of an optical resonator

The dispersion of an eigenfrequency series ω_m is commonly estimated by calculating the deviation from linear dependence $\delta\omega(\Delta\omega) = \omega_m - \omega_0 - m\omega_p$, where $\Delta\omega$ is the continuous extrapolation of $m\omega_p$ and $m = \text{int}(\Delta\omega/\omega_p)$ (see, e.g., [63, 64]). The condition of validity of our model then reads as $|\delta\omega(\Delta\omega_B)| \ll \Delta\omega_{res}$, where $\Delta\omega_{res} = \omega_0/Q$ is resonance width and the quality factor Q is determined by Eq. (12). For the modulation and microresonator parameters considered in Fig. 3, we have $Q \sim 10^7$ and $\Delta\omega_{res} \sim 20$ MHz. For comparison, the deviation $\delta\omega(\Delta\omega_B)$ for the bandwidth of our interest, $\Delta\omega_B = 0.5$ THz, demonstrated in Ref. [64] for LN microresonators with optimized waveguide dispersion is much smaller than 20 MHz. Thus, the negligibly small eigenfrequency dispersion assumed in our model can be achieved experimentally.

Appendix D

Feasible amplitude of the induced refractive index modulation

Several approaches to induce refractive index modulation have been developed. In particular, a spatially uniform capacitor can generate instantaneous modulation $\Delta n_p \cos(\omega_p t)$ corresponding to $v_p = \infty$ (see e.g., [25, 37, 73]). A traveling wave refractive index modulation $\Delta n_0 \cos(\omega_p(t - x/v_p))$ can be introduced

by an RF wave propagating parallel to the optical waveguide (see, e.g., [20-23]). This approach is beneficial for the modulation of photonic circuits with a traveling wave having the phase velocity v_p comparable or equal to the phase velocity of light v_0 . In contrast to these approaches, we are interested here in relatively small traveling wave phase velocities $v_p \ll v_0$. For this purpose, SAWs and bulk acoustic waves generated by an IDT can be used [34, 38, 68-73]. SAWs modulate the refractive index of an optical waveguide through the elasto-optics effect. The SAWs can be enhanced and aligned along an optical waveguide by the combination of a focused IDT and an acoustic waveguide as illustrated in Fig. 2. The characteristic refractive index variation induced by SAWs generated by an IDT in lithium niobate is estimated as $\Delta n_p \sim \frac{1}{2} n_0^3 (r_{33} - p_{33} d_{33}) V/w$, where V is the voltage applied to the IDT, w is the characteristic IDT finger separation. Setting the electro-optic coefficient $r_{33} = 30$ pm/V, the photoelastic coefficient $p_{33} = 0.1$, the piezoelectric coefficient $d_{33} = 6$ pm/V, and assuming $V/w \sim 1$ V/ μm , we find $\Delta n_p \sim 10^{-4}$ at the IDT position.

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Feasibility of a solely acoustic-wave-driven light amplifier

Supplemental Material

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A. Solution of the wave equation in the eikonal (WKB) approximation

We assume that the refractive index is a slow function of time and coordinates and formally introduce slow coordinate and time, $\zeta = \varepsilon x$ and $\tau = \varepsilon t$, where $\varepsilon \sim \omega_p/\omega_0 \ll 1$. We look for the solution of Eq. (1) of the main text in the form [50, 51]:

$$E(x, t) = (U_0(x, t) + \varepsilon U_1(x, t) + \dots) \exp\left(\frac{i}{\varepsilon} S(x, t)\right). \quad (\text{A1})$$

Substituting Eq. (A1) into Eq. (1) and expanding the result in powers of ε , we arrive at a series of coupled equations for $U_m(x, t)$ and $S(x, t)$. In the zero order in ε , we obtain the equation for the eikonal $S(x, t)$ which determines the phase of solution:

$$n^2(x, t) S_t^2 - c^2 S_x^2 = 0. \quad (\text{A2})$$

This equation is reduced to the linear equation

$$n(x, t) S_t + c S_x = 0, \quad (\text{A3})$$

where it is assumed that the speed of light c can have positive or negative sign. Once the solution $S(x, t)$ of Eq. (A3) is found, the amplitude terms $U_m(x, t)$ are determined from linear equations that can be solved successively. In particular, the zero-order term $U_0(x, t)$ of the amplitude of solution is found from the equation:

$$n(x, t) U_{0t} + c U_{0x} + \left(\frac{3}{2} n_t + \frac{c}{2n} n_x\right) U_0 = 0. \quad (\text{A4})$$

For the case of the traveling wave refractive index defined by Eq. (2) with $\alpha_p = 0$, solution of eikonal Eq. (A2) for the field phase and Eq. (A4) for the field amplitude can be found by the introduction of variables

$$\begin{aligned} t' &= t - \frac{x}{v_0}, \\ x' &= x, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A5})$$

Fig. S1. An optical waveguide with the refractive index modulated by a traveling wave with zero attenuation, $\alpha_p = 0$, along the interval $(0, L)$.

where $v = c/n_0$ is the phase velocity of light (Fig. S1). Then, the refractive index in Eq. (2) depends on t' only and Eqs. (A4) and (A5) can be rewritten down as

$$(a + b \cos(\omega_p t')) S_{t'} + v S_{x'} = 0, \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$(a + b \cos(\omega_p t')) U_{0t'} + v U_{0x'} - \delta(t') U = 0, \quad (\text{A7})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a &= 1 - \frac{v_0}{v_p} + i \frac{\eta_0}{n_0}, \quad b = \frac{\Delta n_0}{n_0}, \quad \eta_0 = \frac{\alpha_0 c}{\omega_0}, \\ \delta(t) &= b \omega_p \sin(\omega_p t) \frac{2 + b + 3b \cos(\omega_p t)}{2(1 + b \cos(\omega_p t))}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A8})$$

The general solutions of Eqs. (A3) and (A4) expressed through the original variables x and t are [74]:

$$S(x, t) = \Phi_0(\xi(x, t)), \quad (\text{A9})$$

$$U_0(x, t) = \Phi_1(\xi(x, t)) W\left(t - \frac{x}{v_p}\right), \quad (\text{A10})$$

$$W(t) = \exp\left(\int_0^t \frac{\delta(t) dt}{a + b \cos(\omega_p t)}\right) = \frac{(a + b)\sqrt{1 + b}}{(a + b \cos(\omega_p t))\sqrt{1 + b \cos(\omega_p t)}}.$$

Here $\Phi_k(\xi)$ are arbitrary functions determined by the boundary and initial conditions and

$$\begin{aligned}\xi(x,t) &= x - v \int_0^{t-\frac{x}{v_p}} \frac{dt}{a + b \cos(\omega_p t)} \\ &= x - \frac{2v}{\omega_p \sqrt{a^2 - b^2}} \Xi \left(\sqrt{\frac{a-b}{a+b}}, \left(\frac{\omega_p}{2} \left(t - \frac{x}{v_p} \right) \right) \right).\end{aligned}\quad (\text{A11})$$

Here, function $\Xi(x, y)$ is the smooth continuation of $\arctan(x \cdot \tan(y))$ as a function of y which is convenient to calculate as

$$\Xi(x, y) = \int_0^y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\arctan(x, \tan(y))) dy = \int_0^y \frac{dy}{x^2 \sin^2(y) + \cos^2(y)} \quad (\text{A12})$$

Ignoring the reflected wave, we determine the asymptotic solution of Eq. (1) corresponding to the boundary condition at $x = 0$ (Fig. S1)

$$E^{(in)}(x, t) = \exp \left[i\omega \left(\frac{x}{v_0} - t \right) \right], \quad x < 0, \quad (\text{A13})$$

separating it into the boundary conditions for $S(x, t)$ and $U_0(x, t)$:

$$S(0, t) = -\omega t, \quad (\text{A14})$$

$$U_0(0, t) = 1. \quad (\text{A15})$$

Following the approach of Refs. [8, 9], we introduce function $\bar{t}(\bar{\xi})$ inverse to function $\bar{\xi}(t) = \xi(t, 0)$ which is found from Eq. (A11) as

$$\bar{t}(\bar{\xi}) = -\frac{2}{\omega_p} \Xi \left(\sqrt{\frac{a+b}{a-b}}, \frac{\omega_p}{2v_0} \sqrt{a^2 - b^2} \bar{\xi} \right) \quad (\text{A16})$$

where, again, function $\Xi(x, y)$ is the smooth continuation of $\arctan(x \cdot \tan(y))$ as a function of y defined by Eq. (A12). Using Eqs. (A11)-(A16), we find:

$$\begin{aligned}E(x, t) &= U_0(x, t) \exp(iS(x, t)) \\ S(x, t) &= -\omega \bar{t}(\bar{\xi}(x, t)) = \frac{2\omega}{\omega_p} \Xi \left(\sqrt{\frac{a+b}{a-b}}, \frac{\omega_p}{2v_0} \sqrt{a^2 - b^2} \bar{\xi} \right) \\ U_0(x, t) &= \frac{W \left(t - \frac{x}{v_p} \right)}{W \left(\bar{t}(\bar{\xi}(x, t)) \right)} = \frac{\left(a + b \cos \left(\omega_p \bar{t}(\bar{\xi}(x, t)) \right) \right) \sqrt{1 + b \cos \left(\omega_p \bar{t}(\bar{\xi}(x, t)) \right)}}{\left(a + b \cos \left(\omega_p \left(t - \frac{x}{v_p} \right) \right) \right) \sqrt{1 + b \cos \left(\omega_p \left(t - \frac{x}{v_p} \right) \right)}}.\end{aligned}\quad (\text{A17})$$

The spatial dependence of this solution is characterized by the synchronization parameter

$$\mu = \frac{b}{a} = \frac{\Delta n_0}{n_0 \left(1 - \frac{v_0}{v_p} + i \frac{\eta_0}{n_0} \right)}. \quad (\text{A18})$$

Under the condition of negligible material losses, $\eta_0 = 0$, the synchronization parameter μ is real and there exist two qualitatively different cases of the spatially unstable ($|\mu| > 1$) and spatially stable ($|\mu| < 1$) solutions, corresponding to the synchronous and the asynchronous cases [8, 9]. Fig. S2 presents examples of the characteristic behavior of the normalized field amplitude $|U_0(L, t)|$ at a fixed time $t = 0$ and the time-averaged normalized wave power

$$P_{av}(L) = \frac{\omega_p}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi/\omega_p} U_0(L, t)^2 dt. \quad (\text{A19})$$

as a function of modulation length L .

Fig. S2. The amplitude and time-averaged power of the output wave as a function of modulation length L for different synchronization parameters μ corresponding to close phase velocities v and v_p of the input light and modulation. (a)-(e) The amplitude (left vertical axes) and normalized time-averaged power (right vertical axes) for modulation lengths $0 < L < 0.25$ m. (a) $|\mu| = \infty, v = v_p$ (completely synchronous case); (b) $|\mu| = 2, v = 1.001v_p$ (synchronous case); (c) $|\mu| = 1, v = 1.001v_p$; (d) $|\mu| = 0.5, v = 1.002v_p$ (asynchronous case); (e) $|\mu| = 0.2, v = 1.005v_p$ (asynchronous case); (f) Time-averaged power $P_{av}(L)$ for modulation lengths $0 < L < 1$ m for the relations between v and v_p of plots (a)-(e).

Fig. S2(f) presents $P_{av}(L)$ as a function of modulation length L for different synchronization parameters μ . In this figure, we consider the propagation of light along the lithium niobate waveguide with refractive index $n_0 = 2.2$ modulated with relative amplitude $\Delta n_p/n_0 = 10^{-3}$. The input light frequency and

modulation frequency are set to $\omega_0 = 2\pi \cdot 193$ THz and $\omega_p = 2\pi \cdot 100$ GHz. The purpose of so large modulation amplitude Δn_p and frequency ω_p considered is to evaluate the *largest possible effects of modulation* including the largest possible amplification. To visually resolve the fine spatial oscillations of the wave amplitude, Figs. S2(a)-(e) show the behavior of $|U_0(L, 0)|$ (blue frequently oscillating curves) and $P_{av}(L)$ (bold curves of different color) along the interval $0 < L < 0.25$ m, while Fig. S2(f) shows the behavior of $P_{av}(L)$ over a longer interval $0 < L < 1$ m. It is seen that for $|\mu| > 1$ the wave amplitude $|U_0(L, t)|$ oscillates and grows with L while its time-averaged value grows exponentially. In contrast, for $|\mu| < 1$, both $|U_0(L, 0)|$ and $P_{av}(L)$ remain, respectively, quasiperiodic and periodic as a function of modulation length L .

It is also seen from Fig. S2(f) that, for the parameters considered, the dependencies of the wave amplitude $|U_0(L, 0)|$ and the time-averaged power $P_{av}(L)$ on L are similar for modulation lengths $L < 0.1$ m. Consequently, in this interval, the proximity to the full synchronization condition $v_p = v$ does not enhance the wave amplification, which is always small at these modulation lengths.

Fig. S3. The transmission power and time-averaged power of the output wave as a function of modulation length L for different imaginary parts of refractive index $\eta_0 = \alpha_0 c / \omega_0$ in the synchronous case $|\mu| = 0.2$, $v_p = 1.0005v$. (a) $\eta_0 = 0$. (b) $\eta_0 = 10^{-8}n_0$. (c) $\eta_0 = 10^{-7}n_0$. (d) $\eta_0 = 10^{-6}n_0$.

B. The effect of losses

Material losses can significantly modify the behavior of the propagating wave shown in Fig. S2. Here, we find the effect of relatively small though practically feasible material losses for an ideally dispersionless waveguide. We note that the light propagation loss of a lithium niobate waveguide can be as small as $\alpha_0 = 0.2$ dB/m [65, 66] corresponding to the imaginary part of refractive index $\eta_0 = \alpha_0 c / \omega_0 \sim 10^{-8}$ (see Eq. (2)). In Fig. S3 we consider the effect of broadband dispersionless material losses for the phase velocity relation $v_p = 1.0005v_0$. In this figure, the blue curves show the normalized wave power $|U_0(L, 0)|^2$ as a function of modulation length L at a fixed time, $t = 0$, the black curves show this dependence for the unmodulated waveguide, $\Delta n_p = 0$, and the red curves are the dependencies of time-averaged wave power $P_{av}(L)$ on the modulation length L . We notice that the relation $v_p = 1.0005v_0$ considered in Fig. S3 corresponds to the synchronization parameter $|\mu| = 2$ similar to that for the relation $v_0 = 1.0005v_p$ considered in Fig. S2(b). Consequently, the behavior of the field power shown in Fig. S2(b) and the corresponding time-averaged field power (orange curve in Fig. S2(f)) is similar to those in Fig. S3(a) for $\eta_0 = 0$. We find that the effect of attenuation for $\eta_0 = 10^{-8}$ (Fig. S3(b)) is small for modulation lengths $L < 0.3$ m and grows for larger L . This effect is much stronger for $\eta_0 = 10^{-7}$ (Fig. S3(b)) and for $\eta_0 = 10^{-6}$ (Fig. S3(c)).

C. Transmission amplitude, power, and bandwidth for the synchronous case $v_p = v_0$

In the synchronous lossless case, $v_p = v_0$ and $\eta_0 = 0$ (i.e., $a = 0$), Eq. (A17) is simplified. Setting $\Xi(x, y) = \arctan(x \cdot \tan(y))$, we find

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(x, t) &= U_0(x, t) \exp(iS(x, t)) \\
 S(x, t) &= \frac{2\omega}{\omega_p} \arctan \left(i \tan \left(\frac{i\omega_p b x}{2v_0} - \arctan \left(i \tan \left(\frac{\omega_p}{2} \left(t - \frac{x}{v_p} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 &= \frac{2\omega}{\omega_p} \arctan \left(\frac{\tanh \left(\frac{b\omega_p x}{2v_0} \right) - \tan \left(\frac{\omega_p}{2} \left(t - \frac{x}{v_p} \right) \right)}{1 - \tanh \left(\frac{b\omega_p x}{2v_0} \right) \tan \left(\frac{\omega_p}{2} \left(t - \frac{x}{v_p} \right) \right)} \right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{C1}$$

Next, we simplify Eq. (A17) for the amplitude $U_0(x, t)$ under the same assumption $a = 0$ assuming $\Delta n_p / n_0 \ll 1$. As the result we have:

$$U_0(x, t) = \frac{\cos(\omega_p \bar{t}(\xi(x, t)))}{\cos \left(\omega_p \left(t - \frac{x}{v_p} \right) \right)}. \tag{C2}$$

where

$$\cos(\omega_p \bar{t}(\xi(x, t))) = \left(\cosh \left(\frac{b\omega_p}{v_0} \xi(x, t) \right) \right)^{-1} \tag{C3}$$

Then, from Eqs. (C2) and (C3),

$$U_0(x, t) = \frac{1}{\cosh\left(\frac{b\omega_p x}{v_0}\right) - \sin\left(\omega_p\left(t - \frac{x}{v_p}\right)\right) \sinh\left(\frac{b\omega_p x}{v}\right)}. \quad (C4)$$

Averaging the output power, $P(x, t) = U_0(x, t)^2$, over time we find:

$$P_{av}(x) = \frac{\omega_p}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi/\omega_p} U_0(x, t)^2 dt = \cosh\left(\frac{b\omega_p x}{v_0}\right). \quad (C5)$$

This result coincides with that found for the exactly solvable problem of waveguides with constant impedance [8]. It follows from Eq. (C5) that the average amplification power grows exponentially with modulation length x if $x \gg c/\Delta n_p \omega_p$.

It is seen from Eq. (C4) that for a sufficiently large modulation length x corresponding to $\exp\left(\frac{b\omega_p x}{v_0}\right) \gg 1$ the amplitude $U_0(x, t)$ rapidly changes with time in small intervals $\sin(\omega_p(t - x/v_p))$ is close to unity. We determine the position t_{max} of the maximum slope of $U_0(x, t)$ as a function of time by finding the zeros of its second derivative. Then, the condition of validity of the eikonal approximation, $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} U_0(x, t)|_{t=t_{max}} \ll \omega_0$ yields:

$$\frac{\omega_p}{\omega_0} \ll \exp\left(-\frac{2\Delta n_p \omega_p}{n_0 v_0} x\right). \quad (C6)$$

For a relatively small amplification length $x \ll c/\Delta n_0 \omega_p$, the spectrum of the output light is localized near the input frequency ω_0 . Consequently, it is convenient to introduce the spectrum centered at ω_0 by the expansion:

$$E(x, t) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} U_m^{(c)}(x) \exp(-i\omega_0 t + im\omega_p t), \quad (C7)$$

$$U_m^{(c)}(x) = \frac{\omega_p}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi/\omega_p} E(x, t) \exp(i\omega_0 t - im\omega_p t) dt. \quad (C8)$$

We determine the transmission bandwidth by calculating the integral for the frequency comb amplitude given by Eq. (C8) using the stationary phase method. For brevity, we introduce notations:

$$t_{xt} = \tan\left(\omega_p\left(\frac{x}{v_p} - t\right)\right), \quad t_x = \tanh\left(\frac{b\omega_p x}{2v_0}\right). \quad (C9)$$

The stationary phase time is then found by zeroing the derivative of the phase in the exponent of the integral of Eq. (C8) where $E(x, t)$ is determined by Eq. (C1):

$$\frac{\omega_0(t_x^2 - 1)(t_{xt}^2 + 1)}{t_x^2 t_{xt}^2 + t_x^2 + 4t_x t_{xt} + t_{xt}^2 + 1} + \omega_0 - \omega_p n = 0. \quad (C10)$$

From here, we find

$$t_{xt}^{\pm} = \frac{(\zeta_+ \zeta_-)^{1/2} (t_x^2 - 1)^{1/2} \pm 2t_x \left(\frac{\omega_0}{\omega_p} - n \right)}{\left(n - 2 \frac{\omega_0}{\omega_p} \right) t_x^2 - n}, \quad (\text{C11})$$

$$\zeta_{\pm} = n + \left(n \pm 2 \frac{\omega_0}{\omega_p} \right) t_x. \quad (\text{C12})$$

$\frac{\omega_0}{2\pi}$ (THz)	n_0	v_0 (m/s)	$\frac{\omega_p}{2\pi}$ (GHz)	$\frac{\Delta n_p}{n_0}$
193	2.2	$1.36 \cdot 10^8$	100	10^{-3}

Fig. S4. Transmission amplitude spectra and time-average amplification power at the synchronous condition $v_p = v$ for different modulation lengths $L = 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2,$ and 0.5 m. Parameters of the input light, waveguide, and modulation are indicated at the top of the figure.

From Eq. (C11), the real stationary points exist only if $\zeta_+ \zeta_- \geq 0$. After substitution of the expressions for t_x , ζ_+ , and ζ_- from Eqs. (C11) and (C12) into the latter inequality, we find for the transmission band:

$$\omega_{B1}(x) < \omega < \omega_{B2}(x), \quad \omega_{B1,2} = \omega_0 \left(2 - \exp \left(\pm \frac{\Delta n_p \omega_p}{n_0 v_0} x \right) \right) \quad (\text{C13})$$

with the bandwidth

$$\Delta\omega_B(x) = \omega_{B2}(x) - \omega_{B1}(x) = 2\omega_0 \sinh \left(\frac{\Delta n_p \omega_p}{n_0 v_0} x \right). \quad (\text{C14})$$

Close to the edges of this band, the second derivative of $S(x, t)$ over t tends to zero and the stationary phase method fails. The absence of the real stationary points of the integral in Eq. (C8) outside of this frequency band suggests that the position of the spectral bandwidth of the solution given by Eq. (C1) is determined by Eqs. (C13) and (C14). This result is confirmed by numerical calculations of the spectrum for different modulation lengths $L = 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2,$ and 0.5 m presented in Fig. S4. For a relatively small modulation length $L = 0.01$ m, the average field amplification is negligible, $P_{av}(L) = 1.001$, and the spectral bandwidth is small compared to the input light frequency, $\Delta\nu_B = \Delta\omega_B/2\pi = 18$ THz $\ll \omega_0/2\pi = 193$ THz. At $L = 0.05$ m and 0.1 m, the bandwidth $\Delta\nu_B$ becomes comparable to the input frequency, though the average amplification remains small. For larger modulation lengths L , the left-hand-side bandwidth edge $\omega_{B1}(L)$ becomes negative and exponentially grows with L . Alternatively, for large L the right-hand-side edge $\omega_{B2}(L)$ tends to $2\omega_0$ and the output wave spectrum localizes in the vicinity of $2\omega_0$ as illustrated by the spectrum of the output wave at $L = 0.5$ m in Fig. S4.

Comparing Eqs. (C5) and (C14) we find the relation between the transmission power and bandwidth:

$$P_{av}(x) = \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\Delta\omega_B(x)}{2\omega_0} \right)^2}. \quad (\text{C15})$$

For a relatively small bandwidth, $\Delta\omega_B(L) \ll \omega_0$, we have from Eq. (C15):

$$P_{av}(x) \cong 1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta\omega_B(x)}{2\omega_0} \right)^2. \quad (\text{C16})$$

This result coincides with Eq. (4) of the main text for $v_p = v_0$ and $\alpha_0 = 0$.

D. Wave propagation and wave spectrum in the asynchronous case $|v_p - v_0| \gg \Delta n_p/n_0$

Assuming that

$$\mu = \frac{\Delta n_p v_p}{n_0 |v_p - v_0|} \ll 1 \quad (\text{D1})$$

and keeping the zero and the first order in μ and η_0 terms in the expression for the wave amplitude $U_0(x, t)$ and phase $S(x, t)$ given by Eqs. (A16), (A17), we find:

$$E(x,t) = U_0(x,t) \exp(iS(x,t)),$$

$$S(x,t) = \omega_0 \left(\frac{x}{v_0} - t \right) + i\alpha_0 x + \Omega_p(x) \cos \left(\omega_p \left(t - \frac{(v_0 + v_p)}{2v_0 v_p} x \right) \right), \quad (\text{D2})$$

$$U_0(x,t) = 1 - \Omega_p(x) \frac{\omega_p}{2\omega_0} \left(\frac{v_0}{v_p} - 3 \right) \sin \left(\omega_p \left(t - \frac{(v_0 + v_p)}{2v_0 v_p} x \right) \right).$$

In this equation, we introduce the *modulation index* $\Omega_p(x)$ which characterizes the effect of modulation on the propagation of a wave along the modulation length x :

$$\Omega_p(x) = \frac{2\Delta n_p \omega_0 v_p}{n_0 \omega_p (v_0 - v_p)} \sin \left(\frac{(v_0 - v_p)}{2v_0 v_p} \omega_p x \right). \quad (\text{D3})$$

The structure of the eikonal $S(x,t)$ in Eq. (D2) resembles the expressions known in the theory of optical modulators [19, 20, 24]. In particular, it follows from this equation that, in this case, the effect of material losses is described by the factor $\exp(-\alpha_0 x)$, which is the same as for the stationary (unmodulated) wave propagation. For the case of instantaneous modulation, $v_p = \infty$, Eq. (D3) coincides with that for the absolute value of modulation index found in Ref. [60]. It follows from the expression for $U_0(x)$ in Eq. (D2) that the first order in modulation amplitude Δn_p term in the time-averaged power $P_{av}(x)$ vanishes. Taking into account the second order in Δn_p (more precisely – in μ), we find:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{av}(x) &\cong 1 - 2\alpha_0 x + \frac{(v_0 - 2v_p)(v_0 - 3v_p)}{v_p^2} \left(\Omega_p(x) \frac{\omega_p}{\omega_0} \right)^2 \\ &= 1 - 2\alpha_0 x + \frac{\Delta n_0^2}{4n_0^2} \frac{(v_0 - 2v_p)(v_0 - 3v_p)}{(v_0 - v_p)^2} \sin^2 \left(\frac{v_0 - v_p}{2v_0 v_p} \omega_p x \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D4})$$

This equation shows that, close to the completely synchronous condition $v_0 = v_p$ or, more precisely, for $|v_0 - v_p| \ll v_0$ and modulation lengths satisfying the inequality

$$x \ll x_s = \frac{2v_0 v_p}{\omega_p |v_0 - v_p|}, \quad (\text{D5})$$

the modulation leads to a small wave amplification equal to

$$P_{av}(x) \Big|_{x \ll x_s} \cong 1 - 2\alpha_0 x + \frac{\Delta n_0^2 \omega_p^2}{2c^2} x^2. \quad (\text{D6})$$

This result is similar to that found in Ref. [16] under the same assumption $|\mu| \ll 1$. From Eq. (D6), the modulation length leading to the noticeable amplification of light can be estimated as $x_a = c/(\Delta n_0 \omega_p)$. For the parameters considered here, $\omega_p \sim 2\pi \cdot 100$ GHz, $n_0 = 2.2$, $\Delta n_0/n_0 \sim 10^{-3}$, we have $x_a \sim 20$ cm. Eq. (D4) shows that $P_{av}(x)$ vanishes if the relation between phase velocities is close to $v_0 = 2v_p$ and $v_0 = 3v_p$.

Alternatively, modulation leads to the wave attenuation if $2v_p < v_0 < 3v_p$. It follows from Eq. (D4) that amplification is always small outside the vicinity where $|v_0 - v_p|/v_p \ll 1$. This result is also evident from the solutions given by Eqs. (A16) and (A17) for $|\mu| \ll 1$ and $\Delta n_p/n_0 \ll 1$.

To determine the spectrum of the output wave for $|\mu| \ll 1$, we rewrite Eq. (D2) as

$$E(x, t) = \exp \left[i\omega_0 \left(\frac{x}{v_0} - t \right) - \frac{\omega_0 \eta_0}{c} x + i\Omega_p(x) \cos \left(\omega_p \left(t - \frac{v_0 + v_p}{2v_0 v_p} x \right) - iG_p \right) \right]. \quad (\text{D7})$$

Here we introduce a small parameter

$$G_p = \frac{\omega_p}{2\omega_0} \left(\frac{v_0}{v_p} - 3 \right), \quad |G_p| \ll 1. \quad (\text{D8})$$

Applying the Jacobi-Unger expansion to Eq. (D7) we find for the modulation length $x = L$:

$$E(L, t) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} U_m^{(c)}(L) \exp \left[i(m\omega_p - \omega_0)t \right], \quad (\text{D9})$$

$$U_m^{(c)}(L) = J_m(\Omega_p(L)) \exp \left[-\frac{\omega_0 \eta_0}{v_0} L + \frac{i\pi m}{2} + i\omega_0 \frac{L}{v_0} - im\omega_p \frac{v_0 + v_p}{2v_0 v_p} L + mG_p \right].$$

To estimate the maximum possible amplitude of conversion $\omega_0 \rightarrow \omega_0 + |m|\omega_p$, we note that, while the maximum argument of the Bessel function in Eq. (D9) can be large, $z = \Omega_p(L) \gg 1$, the maximum of $|J_m(z)|$ is always smaller than $2^{-1/2}$ [75]. For $|m| \gg 1$, the $|J_m(z)|$ maximum is defined by its asymptotics equal to $0.674|m|^{-1/3}$ [75], i.e., vanishes very slowly. This maximum is achieved at $z \cong |m|$, while $|J_m(z)|$ rapidly vanishes for $|z| > |m|$. Thus, the frequency comb bandwidth of $E(L, t)$ is determined from Eqs. (D9) and (D3) as

$$\Delta\omega_B(L) = 2\omega_p |\Omega_p(L)| = \frac{4\Delta n_p \omega_0 v_p}{n_0 |v_0 - v_p|} \left| \sin \left(\frac{(v_0 - v_p)}{2v_0 v_p} \omega_p L \right) \right|, \quad (\text{D10})$$

and the amplification of a comb line is determined from the Eqs. (D8) and (D9) by the factor

$$F_m = \exp(mG_p) = \exp \left[m \frac{\omega_p}{2\omega_0} \left(\frac{v_0}{v_p} - 3 \right) \right]. \quad (\text{D11})$$

Since in the eikonal approximation considered $|G_p| \ll 1$, the factor F_m can be large only for sufficiently large positive comb line numbers m . From Eqs. (D10) and (D11), we find the maximum possible amplification takes place for the maximum positive $m = |\Omega_p(x)|$ within this bandwidth. Then, we find from Eq. (D3) for $\Omega_p(x)$ that the amplification effect defined by F_m is always small away from the synchronous condition, confirming the general result directly following from Eq. (D4).

$\frac{\omega_0}{2\pi}$ (THz)	n_0	v_0 (m/s)	$\frac{\omega_p}{2\pi}$ (GHz)	$\frac{\Delta n_p}{n_0}$	$\frac{\eta_0}{n_0}$	α_0 (dB/m)
193	2.2	$1.36 \cdot 10^8$	100	10^{-3}	10^{-6}	79

Fig. S5. (a) Dependences of modulation index $\Omega_p(L)$ on the modulation length L for close phase velocities, $v_p = 1.05v$, in the asynchronous case $|\mu| = 0.02$ (light blue curve), for instantaneous modulation, $v_p = \infty$ (blue curve), and for the reverse modulation $v_p = -1.05v$ (black curve). (b) Dependences of the reduced eikonal, $S(L, 0) - \omega_0 L/v_0$, on the modulation length L for the completely synchronous modulation, $v_p = v$ (dimmed light blue curve), $v_p = 1.05v$ (light blue curve), $v_p = \infty$ (blue curve), and $v_p = -1.05v$ (black curve). (c), (d), and (e) The transmission amplitudes for (c) $v_p = 1.05v$, (d) $v_p = \infty$, and (e) $v_p = -1.05v$ for different modulation lengths L indicated in the plots of this figure.

A dramatic enhancement of the spectral bandwidth generated by a traveling wave having the phase velocity v_p close to v_0 (though still for a small synchronization parameter $|\mu| \ll 1$), as compared to the bandwidth generated by the instantaneous modulation with $v_p = \infty$ and reverse modulation with the reverse sign of v_p , is evidenced from Fig. S5. The reason for the enhancement is a much greater value of the modulation index $\Omega_p(L)$ at $v_p \cong v_0$. The parameters of light, waveguide, and modulation are indicated at the top of this figure. For the waveguide with these parameters, the value of $\Omega_p(L)$ achieves 81 at $L = 14.3$ mm (Fig. S5(a)) at $v_p = 1.05v$, though remains much smaller for instantaneous and reverse modulations when $v_p = \infty$ and $v_p = -1.05v_0$, respectively. Fig. S5(b) shows the dependences of the reduced eikonal, $S(x_p, 0) - \omega_0 x_p / v_0$, on the modulation length for the same phase velocity relations as well as for the completely synchronous case $v_p = v_0$. It is seen that the oscillation amplitude of the eikonal as a function of modulation length is proportional to the local modulation index, as directly follows from Eq. (D2). Figs. S5(c), (d), and (e) show the frequency comb spectra of solutions for (c) $v_p = 1.05v_0$, (d) $v_p = \infty$, and (e) $v_p = -1.05v$ for different modulation lengths L indicated in the plot (b) of this figure. It is seen that, in accordance with Eq. (D10), the generated frequency comb bandwidth is proportional to the value of corresponding modulation index shown in Fig. S5(a). We note that the dramatic reduction of modulation effect of the reverse vs. the direct modulation manifests the strong nonreciprocity of propagation.

In contrast to the optical frequency comb bandwidth, the total amplification of light induced by modulation remains small for $\Delta\omega_B(x) \ll \omega_0$. Indeed, comparing Eq. (D10) and Eq. (D4), we find:

$$P_{av}(x) \cong 1 - 2\alpha_0 x + \frac{(v_0 - 2v_p)(v_0 - 3v_p)}{v_p^2} \left(\frac{\Delta\omega_B(x)}{4\omega_0} \right)^2. \quad (\text{D12})$$

At zero material attenuation, $\alpha_0 = 0$, this result coincides with Eq. (4) of the main text. In particular, close to the completely synchronous condition $v_p = v_0$

$$P_{av}(x)|_{v_p \rightarrow v_0} = 1 - 2\alpha_0 x + \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{\Delta\omega_B(x)}{\omega_0} \right)^2. \quad (\text{D13})$$

Remarkably, this equation coincides with Eq. (C16) for relatively small bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B \ll \omega_0$. Thus, the relation between the transmission power and bandwidth defined by Eq. (D12) is equally valid for the asynchronous and synchronous cases.

E. Solution of the wave equation by the perturbation theory

For sufficiently small modulation of the refractive index Δn_p and small modulation index $|\Omega_p| \ll 1$, solution of the wave equation, Eq. (1), can be found by the perturbation theory. We rewrite Eq. (1) as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \left((n_0 + \Delta n(x, t))^2 E \right)}{\partial t^2} - c^2 \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x^2} = 0 \quad (\text{E1})$$

and solve it by perturbations over $\Delta n(x, t)$,

$$E(x, t) = E^{(0)}(x, t) + E^{(1)}(x, t) + E^{(2)}(x, t) \dots, \quad (\text{E2})$$

where $\Psi^\pm(t)$ are arbitrary functions. The general solution of our interest, which is used in calculations of the transmission amplitude through an optical resonator corresponds to $\Psi^-(t) \equiv 0$, since it includes only optical waves propagating along a positive direction of axis x . In the zero, first, and second order, we have

$$n_0^2 E_{tt}^{(0)} - c^2 E_{xx}^{(0)} = 0, \quad (\text{E3})$$

$$n_0^2 E_{tt}^{(1)} - c^2 E_{xx}^{(1)} = -2n_0 \left(\Delta n(x, t) E^{(0)} \right)_{tt}, \quad (\text{E4})$$

$$n_0^2 E_{tt}^{(2)} - c^2 E_{xx}^{(2)} = -2n_0 \left(\Delta n^2 E^{(0)} \right)_{tt} - 2n_0 \left(\Delta n E^{(1)} \right)_{tt}. \quad (\text{E5})$$

Here subindices x and t denote partial derivatives. The general solution of Eq. (E4) can be presented as

$$E_{gen}^{(1)}(x, t) = E^{(1)}(x, t) + \Psi^+ \left(t - \frac{x}{v_0} \right) + \Psi^- \left(t + \frac{x}{v_0} \right), \quad (\text{E6})$$

where $E^{(1)}(x, t)$ is a particular solution of Eq. (E4) and $\Psi^\pm(t)$ are relatively small arbitrary functions, $|\Psi^\pm(t)| \ll 1$.

The refractive index variation considered in the main text is

$$\Delta n(x, t) = \Delta n_{p0} \exp(-\alpha_p x) \cos \left(\omega_p \left(t - \frac{x}{v_p} \right) \right) + i \frac{\alpha_0 c}{\omega_0}. \quad (\text{E7})$$

We choose the zero-order solution of Eq. (E1) as

$$E^{(0)}(x, t) = \exp \left[i \omega_0 \left(\frac{x}{v_0} - t \right) - \alpha_0 x \right]. \quad (\text{E8})$$

To solve Eq. (E4) with $E^{(0)}(0, t)$ defined by Eq. (E8) and refractive index variation defined by Eq. (E7), we separate Eq. (E4) into two equations for $E^{(1)(+)}(x, t)$ and $E^{(1)(-)}(x, t)$:

$$n_0^2 E_{tt}^{(1)(\pm)} - c^2 E_{xx}^{(1)(\pm)} = -n_0 \Delta n_{p0} \left(\exp \left(\pm i \omega_p \left(\frac{x}{v_p} - t \right) + i \omega_0 \left(\frac{x}{v_0} - t \right) - (\alpha_0 + \alpha_p) x \right) \right)_{tt}. \quad (\text{E9})$$

Then, a particular solution of Eq. (E4) vanishing for $\Delta n(x, t) \rightarrow 0$ is

$$E^{(1)}(x, t) = E^{(1)(+)}(x, t) + E^{(1)(-)}(x, t). \quad (\text{E10})$$

Functions $E^{(1)(\pm)}(x, t)$ can be found in the form proportional to the right-hand side function of Eq. (E9):

$$E^{(1)(\pm)}(x, t) = \Delta U_0^\pm \exp \left(\pm i \omega_p \left(\frac{x}{v_p} - t \right) + i \omega_0 \left(\frac{x}{v_0} - t \right) - (\alpha_0 + \alpha_p) x \right). \quad (\text{E11})$$

Substituting Eq. (E11) into Eq. (E9) and taking into account that $\alpha_0 \ll \alpha_p$ for the cases of our interest (we consider $\alpha_0 \lesssim 10$ dB/m and $\alpha_p \gtrsim 10$ dB/cm), we find:

$$\Delta U_0^\pm = \frac{\Delta n_p v_p^2 (\omega_0 \pm \omega_p)^2}{n_0 \left[\pm \omega_p (v_0 - v_p) + i \alpha_p v_0 v_p \right] \left[2 \omega_0 v_p \pm \omega_p (v_0 + v_p) + i \alpha_p v_0 v_p \right]}. \quad (\text{E12})$$

Choosing an appropriate function $\Psi^+(t)$ in Eq. (E6), we find the first order solution of Eq. (E1) satisfying the boundary condition $E^{(1)}(0, t) = 0$:

$$E^{(1)}(x, t) = E^{(0)}(x, t) \sum_{\pm} \left(\Delta U_0^{\pm} \exp(\mp i \omega_p t) W^{\pm}(x) \right), \quad (\text{E13})$$

$$W^{\pm}(x) = \exp\left(\pm i \frac{\omega_p x}{v_p} - \alpha_p x\right) - \exp\left(\pm i \frac{\omega_p x}{v_0}\right). \quad (\text{E14})$$

Solution defined by Eqs. (E2), (E8), (E12), (E13), and (E14) can be directly transformed to the form presented by Eqs. (A1)-(A5) in the End Matter.

Here we are only interested in the part of second order solution $E^{(2)}(x, t)$ of Eq. (E1) which contributes to the averaged over time output transmission power $|E(x, t)|^2$ at the Brillouin resonance modulation frequency $\omega_p^{(res)}$ determined by Eq. (5) for co-propagating light and modulating wave, $v_0, v_p > 0$, and under the condition $\exp(-\alpha_p L) \ll 1$. Direct calculations show that close to the resonance $\omega_p^{(res)}$ and under the commonly valid condition $\alpha_p v_0 \ll \omega_0$ the contribution of the second order solution $E^{(2)}(L, t)$ to the averaged output power is much smaller than the contribution of the first order. Consequently, we find for the time-averaged power

$$P_{av}(L) = \left\langle |E(L, t)|^2 \right\rangle_t \cong 1 + \left| \Delta U_{res}^- \right|^2. \quad (\text{E15})$$

where ΔU_{res}^- is the value of ΔU_0^- at the resonance modulation frequency $\omega_p^{(res)}$,

$$\Delta U_{res}^- = \frac{i \Delta n_p \omega_0}{2 n_0 \alpha_p v_0}. \quad (\text{E16})$$

After including the effect of optical attenuation, Eqs. (E15) and (E16) lead to Eq. (6) of the main text.

For contra-propagating light and modulating waves, when $v_0 > 0$ and $v_p < 0$, the Brillouin resonance condition, Eq. (5), is replaced by

$$\omega_p = \omega_p^{(res)} = -\frac{2 \omega_0 v_p}{v_0 - v_p}. \quad (\text{E17})$$

Then the term proportional to ΔU_0^+ becomes dominant in the solution defined by Eq. (E13). At the exact Brillouin resonance, we find $\Delta U_{res}^+ = \Delta U_{res}^-$ and the time averaged power is, again, determined by Eqs. (E15) and (E16).

F. Transmission amplitude through an optical resonator

The derivation of Eq. (B1) of the End Matter for the transmission amplitude through a racetrack optical resonator modulated by a traveling wave (Fig. 1(b)) follows the approach of Ref. [60] where a similar problem was reduced to an exactly solvable functional equation. *In the first order over $\Delta n_p/n_0$ and η_0/n_0 of the eikonal and perturbation theories*, the general solution of Eq. (1) of the main text can be written down as

$$E(x, t) = \exp\left[i \omega_0 \left(\frac{x}{v_0} - t \right) - \frac{\omega_0 \eta_0}{c} x + i \Omega_p(x) \cos\left(\omega_p \left(t - \frac{v_0 + v_p}{2 v_0 v_p} x \right) - i G_p(x) \right) \right] \Phi\left(t - \frac{x}{v_0} \right), \quad (\text{F1})$$

where $\Phi(t)$ is an arbitrary function. This expression directly follows from Eqs. (D7), (A9), and (A10) considered in the eikonal approximation and from Eq. (E6), and Eqs. (A2) and (A3) of the End Matter considered with the perturbation theory. In the eikonal approximation and for the traveling wave attenuation equal to zero, $\alpha_p = 0$, the modulation index $\Omega_p(x)$ and phase $iG_p(x)$ are determined by Eqs. (D3) and (D8). In the first order perturbation theory, these functions are determined by Eq. (A3) of the End Matter. Assuming that the field inside the racetrack resonator can be expressed by Eq. (F1) and substituting this solution into the coupled wave equations, Eq. (7), we arrive at the functional equation for $\Phi(t)$

$$\Phi(t) = \tau A(t)\Phi(t-T) - \kappa, \quad (\text{F2})$$

where

$$A(t) = \exp \left[i\omega_0 T - \frac{\eta_0}{n_0} \omega_0 T + i\Omega_p(L) \cos \left(\omega_p \left(t - \frac{(v_0 + v_p)}{2v_0 v_p} L - iG_p(L) \right) \right) \right]. \quad (\text{F3})$$

Without reducing generality, we assume here that the perimeter of the resonator is $2L$, while the modulation length is equal to L . Consequently, the circulation time of light is $T = 2L/v_0$. Solution of Eq. (F2) presented in Appendix C of Ref. [60] leads to

$$U_m^{(c)} = \tau \delta_{0m} - \kappa^2 \exp \left[im \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{\omega_p T}{2} - \frac{\omega_p (v_0 + v_p)}{2v_0 v_p} L - iG_p(L) \right) \right] \times \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} J_m(\sigma_{n+1} \Omega_p(L)) \tau^n \exp \left[(n+1) \left(-\frac{im}{2} \omega_p T + i\omega_0 T - 2\alpha_0 L \right) \right], \quad (\text{F4})$$

$$\sigma_n = \frac{\sin \left(\frac{n}{2} \omega_p T \right)}{\sin \left(\frac{1}{2} \omega_p T \right)}, \quad T = \frac{2L}{v_0}.$$

This equation coincides with Eq. (B1) of Appendix B.

Significant amplification of light demonstrated in Fig. 3 of the main text takes place near the Brillouin resonance phase velocity $v_p \cong \omega_p v_0 / 2\omega_0$ which is much smaller than the phase velocity of light, $v_p \ll v_0$. For comparison, Fig. S6 shows the behavior of the transmission spectrum for different relations between phase velocities v_p and v_0 . To enhance the amplification effect away from the Brillouin resonance condition of Eq. (5), we consider a large modulation frequency, $\omega_p = 30$ GHz, and modulation index $\Delta n_p = 2 \cdot 10^{-4} n_0$, where $n_0 = 2.2$ is the refractive index of the lithium niobate, and a small coupling coefficient $\kappa = 0.005$. These modulation parameters are not currently feasible simultaneously, though useful for better understanding of the amplification effect. The modulation frequency offset $\Delta\omega_p$ is chosen to arrive at the resonator bandwidth close to $\Delta\omega_B = 10$ THz, which includes up to ~ 300 comb lines. The microresonator waveguide length $2L = 4.54$ mm was chosen to arrive at the condition close to the modulation resonance $\omega_p T = 2\omega_p L / v_0 = 2\pi$. The system parameters common for all plots are shown on the top of Fig. S6, while the parameters specific for each of the plots are shown on the top of individual plots (a)-(f). To estimate a feasible *maximum* amplification effect in the case of instantaneous ($v_p = \infty$) close to synchronous ($v_p = 1.05v_0$), and marginally small phase velocity ($v_p = 0.01v_0$) modulations, we set the imaginary part of refractive index in Figs. S6(a), (b), and (c) equal to $\eta_0 = 10^{-9} n_0$ corresponding to the material loss $\alpha_0 = 0.077$ dB/m. In particular, in Fig. S6(a) we consider the instantaneous modulation

with $v_p = \infty$. In this case, the modulation index found from Eq. (D3) is $\Omega_p = 3.86$ and the modulation frequency offset corresponding to the bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B = 10$ THz is $\Delta v_p = \Delta\omega_p/2\pi = 24.6$ MHz. The spectrum shown in Fig. S6(b) corresponds to $v_p = 1.05v_0$, i.e., is close to the synchronous modulation. In both cases, the effect of amplification appeared to be negligible. Next, in Fig. S6(c), we consider the case of small traveling wave phase velocity, $v_p = 0.01v_0$, corresponding to much smaller $\Omega_p = -0.039$ and $\Delta v_p = -0.25$ MHz. In this case, the effect of the amplification factor F_m defined by Eq. (D11) entering Eq. (F4) is clearly visible. This factor leads to the attenuation of the transmission spectrum for negative m and its amplification for positive m . However, the total amplification of the input wave power is still small, $P_{av} = 0.19$ dB. To illustrate the feasibility of amplification for smaller phase velocities v_p , in Figs. S6(d), (e), and (f), we set $v_p = 0.001v_0$. This value still satisfies the eikonal condition of slowness of the modulation in space given by Eq. (3). However, the value of v_p cannot be reduced further within the correctness of the eikonal approximation.

Fig. S6. The resonant transmission power spectra for a racetrack resonator. The system parameters are indicated on the top of the figure. Plots (a)-(f) correspond to different traveling wave velocities v_p and waveguide propagation losses α_0 .

Figs. S6(d), (e), and (f) show that, to arrive at substantial amplification of light, the transmission loss of the waveguide of the optical resonator should be exceptionally small. In these figures, the imaginary part of refractive index η_0 is set to $5 \cdot 10^{-9}n_0$ (Fig. S6(d)), $4 \cdot 10^{-9}n_0$ (Fig. S6(e)), and $3 \cdot 10^{-9}n_0$ (Fig. S6(f)).

These values correspond, respectively, to the light attenuation of $\alpha_0 = 0.39$, 0.31, and 0.23 dB/m respectively. The latter values are comparable to the attenuation of 0.2 dB/m recently achieved in a lithium niobate waveguide [65, 66]. Fig. S6(d) shows that the modulation-induced amplification is not sufficient to overcome the attenuation of 0.39 dB/m. However, Fig. S6(e) demonstrates a small full amplification of 1.13 dB for the waveguide loss of 0.31 dB/m. Finally, for a waveguide with propagation loss of 0.23 dB/m achieved in [65], Fig. S6(f) demonstrates a substantial amplification of the input wave power by 24.3 dB as well as the amplification of individual comb line powers.

For instantaneous modulation, $v_p/v_0 = \infty$ (Fig. S6(a)), which is commonly used for the optical frequency comb generation, and also close to the synchronous modulation, $v_p \cong v_0$ (Fig. S6(b)), the frequency comb distribution is very close to symmetric. However, with decreasing the traveling wave phase velocity v_p , the transmission power is vanishing at the lower frequency side and increasing at the higher frequency side (Figs. S6(c)-(f)). In particular, it is seen in Figs. S6(d)-(f) that for very small $v_p/v_0 = 0.001$ the lower frequency side becomes very small too. At much smaller v_p/v_0 corresponding to the Brillouin resonance condition (Eq. (5)) considered in Fig. 3, the lower frequency spectrum is minimized.

In the particular case of $\tau = 0$ and $\kappa = 1$, light is completely transmitted from the input waveguide to the resonator and, after a single roundtrip, completely transmitted back. In this case, only the first term with $n = 0$ in the sum over n in Eq. (F4) is not zero. Then, Eq. (F4) describes the propagation through a waveguide and coincides with Eq. (D9). For small modulation index $|\Omega_p(L)| \ll 1$, at the exact Brillouin resonance defined by Eq. (5), and for the attenuation length of modulation smaller than the half roundtrip length of the resonator, $\exp(-\alpha_p L) \ll 1$, we find:

$$\exp(\text{Re}(G_p(L))) = 2 \left(\frac{\omega_0}{\alpha_p v_0} \right)^{1/2}, \quad (\text{F5})$$

$$\Omega_p(L) = \frac{\Delta n_p v_p}{n_0 \omega_p \alpha_p^{1/2}} \left(\frac{\omega_0}{v_0} \right)^{3/2}. \quad (\text{F6})$$

Then the time-averaged transmission power is found as

$$P_{av}(L) = |U_0^{(c)}|^2 + |U_1^{(c)}|^2 = 1 + \left(\frac{\Delta n_p \omega_0}{2n_0 \alpha_p v_0} \right)^2 - 4\alpha_p L \quad (\text{F7})$$

and coincides with Eq. (6) where the waveguide length L is replaced by the roundtrip length $2L$ of the resonator. In deriving Eq. (F7), we neglect the contribution of the higher order terms $U_m^{(c)}$ with $|m| > 1$ assuming that $|\Omega_p(L)| \exp(\text{Re}(G(L))) = \Delta n_p \omega_0 / (2n_0 \alpha_p v_0) \ll 1$ and $\exp(\text{Re}(G(L))) \gg 1$.

Consider now a racetrack optical resonator under similar conditions leading to Eqs. (F5) and (F6) for a small waveguide-resonator coupling κ (Fig. 1(b)) so that

$$\tau \cong 1 - \frac{\kappa^2}{2}, \quad \kappa \ll 1. \quad (\text{F8})$$

At the exact resonance condition of Eq. (10), the contribution of term $\omega_0 T = 2\pi q$ in the exponent in Eq. (F4) is cancelled. Then, assuming that the modulation frequency ω_p is close to the resonance, i.e.,

$$\omega_p T = 2\pi + \Delta\omega_p T, \quad |\Delta\omega_p T| \ll 1, \quad (\text{F9})$$

we rewrite σ_n defined in Eq. (F4) as

$$\sigma_n = \frac{(-1)^n 2 \sin\left(\frac{n}{2} \Delta\omega_p T\right)}{\omega_p T}. \quad (\text{F10})$$

Assuming, again, $|\Omega_p(L)| \ll 1$, and the exact Brillouin resonance defined by Eq. (5) (the conditions leading to Eqs. (F5) and (F6)), we find

$$J_m(\sigma_{n+1} \Omega_p(L)) \cong \frac{(-1)^{\frac{(1-\text{sign}(m))}{2}m}}{|m|!} \left(\frac{\sigma_{n+1} \Omega_p(L)}{2}\right)^{|m|} = \frac{(-1)^{\frac{(1-\text{sign}(m))}{2}m}}{|m|!} \left(e^{i\pi(n+1)} \frac{\sin\left(\frac{n+1}{2} \Delta\omega_p T\right)}{\Delta\omega_p T} \Omega_p(L) \right)^{|m|}. \quad (\text{F11})$$

Under these conditions, the terms under the sum of Eq. (F4) become slow functions of n . Then, replacing this sum by the integral, we find:

$$U_m^{(c)} = \tau \delta_{0m} - \frac{(-1)^{\frac{(1-\text{sign}(m))}{2}m}}{m!} \frac{\kappa^2}{\omega_p T} \left(\frac{\Omega_p(L)}{\Delta\omega_p T}\right)^m \exp\left[im\left(-\frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{\Delta\omega_p T}{2} - \frac{\omega_p(v_0 + v_p)}{2v_0 v_p} L - iG_p(L)\right)\right] \times \int_0^\infty \sin^m\left(\frac{n}{2} \Delta\omega_p T\right) \exp\left[-n\left(\frac{im}{2} \Delta\omega_p T + 2\alpha_0 L + \frac{\kappa^2}{2}\right)\right] dn. \quad (\text{F12})$$

At $m = 0$, the result of this expression is real, while for $m > 0$ the first term $\tau \delta_{0m}$ is zeroed. Having this in mind and expressing the integral in Eq. (F12) through the Gamma functions, we find for the absolute value of the frequency comb amplitudes:

$$\left|U_m^{(c)}\right| = \left| \tau \delta_{0m} - \frac{i\kappa^2}{\Delta\omega_p T} \left(\frac{\Omega_p(L)}{2\Delta\omega_p T}\right)^{|m|} \frac{\Gamma\left(i\frac{4\alpha_0 L + \kappa^2}{\Delta\omega_p T}\right)}{\Gamma\left(|m| + 1 + i\frac{4\alpha_0 L + \kappa^2}{\Delta\omega_p T}\right)} e^{m\text{Re}(G_p(L))} \right|. \quad (\text{F13})$$

It follows from the derivation of Eq. (F13) that it is valid for small modulation index and in the vicinity of the modulation resonance:

$$|\Omega_p(L)| \ll 1, \quad \Delta\omega_p T \ll 1. \quad (\text{F14})$$

For microresonator and modulation parameters considered in Fig. 3 of the main text, we have $|\Omega_p(L)| \sim 10^{-4}$ and $\Delta\omega_p T \lesssim 10^{-3}$, i.e., these conditions are well satisfied. Fig. S7 shows excellent agreement of numerical results considered in Fig. 3 found from Eq. (F4) with calculations using analytical expression of Eq. (F13). In particular, we found that in all examples considered in Figs. 3 and S7, the difference between the calculated total output powers P_{av} is less than 0.02 dB.

L (mm)	$\frac{\omega_0}{2\pi}$ (THz)	n_0	v_0 (m/s)	v_p (m/s)
6.89	193	2.2	$1.36 \cdot 10^8$	3500

Fig. S7. Comparison of the resonant transmission power spectra for a racetrack resonator calculated using Eqs. (F4) and (F13). The plots (a), (b), ..., (f) calculated with Eq. (4) are identical to the plots (a), (b), ..., (f) in Fig. 3 of the main text.

At the exact Brillouin resonance, Eq. (F13) can be further simplified using the expressions for $\Omega_p(L)$ and $\exp(\text{Re}(G_p(L)))$ given by Eqs. (F5) and (F6) and relation $Tv_0 = 2L$:

$$|U_m^{(c)}| = \left| \tau \delta_{0m} - \frac{ik^2}{\Delta\omega_p T} \left(\frac{\Delta n_p \omega_0}{4n_0 \Delta\omega_p L \alpha_p} \right)^{|m|} \frac{\Gamma \left(i \frac{4\alpha_0 L + \kappa^2}{\Delta\omega_p T} \right)}{\Gamma \left(|m| + 1 + i \frac{4\alpha_0 L + \kappa^2}{\Delta\omega_p T} \right)} \right|. \quad (\text{F15})$$

From this equation, assuming large comb number $m \gg 1$, we estimate the value of $m = m_{max}$ corresponding to the maximum of $|U_m^{(c)}|$ and define the transmission bandwidth as $\Delta\omega_B = 2m_{max}\omega_p$. As the result, we find

$$\Delta\omega_B = 2m_{max}\omega_p = \frac{\Delta n_p \omega_0 \omega_p}{2n_0 \Delta\omega_p L \alpha_p}. \quad (\text{F16})$$

As a necessary condition of the amplification effect, we also find from Eq. (F15)

$$m_{max} = \frac{\Delta\omega_B}{2\omega_p} = \frac{\Delta n_p \omega_0}{4n_0 \Delta\omega_p L \alpha_p} \gg 1. \quad (\text{F17})$$

As expected, Eqs. (16) and (17) show that small shift $\Delta\omega_p$ from the modulation resonance required for amplification necessitates the increase in transmission bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$. Eq. (F16) estimates the dependence of the transmission bandwidth on the system parameters with reasonable accuracy. For example, comparing Figs. 3(a) and 3(c), we find that, to keep the same transmission bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B \cong 0.5$ THz, increasing the modulation attenuation α_p by a factor of two, from 30 dB/cm to 60 dB/cm, requires the reduction of $\Delta\omega_p$ from 4 MHz to 2 MHz, in agreement with Eq. (F16). Comparing Figs. 3(a) and 3(b), we find that, for the same purpose, decreasing the refractive index modulation Δn_p from $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to $5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ by a factor of 4 requires decreasing the offset $\Delta\omega_p$ from the resonance from 4 MHz to 0.7 MHz by a comparable factor of 5.7. Comparing Figs. 3(a) and 3(f), we find that increasing $\Delta\omega_p$ from 4 MHz to 10 MHz, reduces the transmission bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$ by approximately a factor of 2 in a reasonable agreement with Eq. (F16). On the other hand, comparison of Figs. 3(a) and 3(d) shows that, in accordance with Eq. (F16), variation of the waveguide attenuation α_0 does not affect the transmission bandwidth $\Delta\omega_B$.